

Introducing End-to-End Location Awareness in Packet-Optical Networks

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Abstract

This paper discusses the deployment of End-to-End packet-optical connectivity services over an edge-cloud continuum, considering the importance of location awareness. It proposes architecture, data models, and placement algorithms for provisioning and updating these services in the ADRENALINE Testbed using the ETSI TeraFlowSDN controller. ©2023 The Author(s)

Introduction

Several challenges need to be overcome when looking at the deployment of Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM) services over a distributed edge and cloud infrastructure^[1]. Firstly, we need unified computing, storage, and networking resources management. In this respect, the End-to-End SDN Controller (also known as SDN orchestrator, e.g. TeraFlowSDN), together with an NFV orchestrator (e.g., Open-Source MANO), will be able to deploy integrated services (i.e., to provision cloud and edge computing resources and connectivity between them) and optimize the cloud and network resources (i.e., packet/optical) concurrently. Secondly, we must address multi-domain networking, where resources must be assigned in each technological domain and combined for an end-to-end service.

Future services are deployed close to the end user, which requires an edge-cloud continuum. It refers to a distributed computing infrastructure that spans from the edge of the network (where end devices reside) to the cloud (where data centers and servers reside). It encompasses a range of resources and services that can be utilized to process and store data closer to the source, providing low-latency and high-bandwidth connectivity, while also leveraging the scalability and processing power of cloud computing. The introduction of edge-cloud continuum has a significant impact in Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) scenarios, where latency aspect plays a significant role.

Location is a critical component of many V2X services as it provides contextual information about the surrounding environment. One example is collision avoidance, where vehicles can exchange location information to avoid collisions.

Location also plays a significant role in hierarchical computing architecture, which is an emerg-

ing technology that has the potential to transform the way computing is done by allowing the orchestration of end devices, the edge, and the cloud. In a survey conducted by Ren et al.^[2], various related research issues in this architecture were presented. The survey compares different network computing paradigms and discusses different research issues such as computation offloading, caching, including location awareness.

It is in this sense, where the introduction of location-awareness in end-to-end connectivity services and in network topologies is indispensable. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first paper that considers provisioning and updating of end-to-end connectivity service taking into consideration that location-aware connectivity services might need service endpoint migration due to the dynamic nature of joint edge-cloud continuum and the provisioning of services to moving end users.

This paper presents the proposed architecture for the provisioning and update of the aforementioned connectivity services, as well as details of the augmented data models. Moreover, a location allocation algorithm is presented to provide endpoint selection based on location. Finally, we have experimentally evaluated the proposed solution in ADRENALINE Testbed using ETSI TeraFlowSDN controller^[3].

Proposed architecture

The proposed architecture is depicted in Fig. 1.a. On top, the internal cloud-native architecture of ETSI TeraFlowSDN (TFS) is depicted, while below it is shown the controlled multi-domain scenario, that considers E2E connectivity services. The TFS architecture was introduced in^[4]. It divides the main components of the SDN controller into micro-services dedicated to specific

Fig. 1: a) Proposed architecture for E2E location-aware services, including SDN controller necessary components; and b) Internal SDN controller modified data models to support location-aware services.

functionalities of the SDN controller. TFS provides extended support for OpenConfig-based routers and interaction with optical SDN controllers through the ONF Transport API.

The proposed scenario in Fig. 1.a shows a connected vehicle that might be consuming services from a specific edge computing node, that in turn is connected to a DC service. As the vehicle moves, the services might be migrated to another edge computing location. This triggers the update of the connectivity services for the E2E connection towards the DC services.

The introduction of location awareness in transport networks (i.e., including packet and optical domains) requires the introduction of novel concepts to several SDN-based data models. The most affected data models are the ones related to service endpoints, which refer to the network endpoints where connectivity services might be requested. Moreover, connectivity service needs also to include a new constraint that is based on location coordinates or specific region. The proposed modified data models for internal TFS usage are also depicted in Fig. 1.b.

The workflow in Fig. 2.a is described in two phases (service establishment and follow-me service). Service establishment starts with the request to create a new connectivity service between a specific endpoint (e.g., DC location) and the closest endpoint to a location (step 1). The request is processed by SDN controller NBI and forwards it using TFS internal data model to Service component (step 2). There, location constraints and network topology endpoints are matched in order to best provision the necessary endpoints depending on the location. The E2E connection is created following the described workflow in^[3], and properly notified (steps 3-4).

Follow-me service phase starts with an update of the service that is provided including the new

location (steps 5-6). A new endpoint is computed and then a new path computed (steps 7-8) and the service is updated following a break-before-make strategy. The old service is removed (steps 9-12), and the service with updated endpoints is provisioned (steps 13-16). Finally, response is provided to the user (steps 17-18).

To provide location-aware services to TFS, three components have been modified. First, the Context module database has been extended to support the data models showed in Fig. 1.b. The Device module was also extended to retrieve the location data from the network devices. Finally, in the Service module, the algorithm to retrieve the closest access node was implemented.

The proposed algorithm aims to create a service between a data center (DC) and a user by identifying the nearest access edge node to the user's location. To achieve this, the algorithm computes the geographical distance between each of the access edge nodes and the user's location provided in the connectivity service request. Geographical distance can be computed using various methods, but one commonly used approach is to calculate the distance between two points on the Earth's surface using the Haversine formula, which takes into account the radius of the Earth and the latitude and longitude of the two points to calculate their distance. By selecting the nearest access edge node to the user, the algorithm can establish a connection between the user and the network with minimal latency and optimal performance.

Experimental Evaluation

The proposed scenario is depicted in Fig. 1.a. In a basic topology, we have included the GPS location for three different service end points connected to the edge nodes. The user node can then connect to the DC by means of the closest

Fig. 2: a) Sequence diagram of provisioning and update of a location-aware service; b) Histogram of the time spent on the location selection algorithm; and c) Wireshark capture of a location-aware service provision and update.

edge node, depending on it is present location, which is introduced as a constraint to the connectivity service request/update.

Fig. 2.a shows the Wireshark capture of the creation of a location-aware connectivity service and it is updated with a new location. The 1st packet corresponds to the creation of the connectivity service, while the 2nd packet corresponds to it is acknowledged. The 3rd packet corresponds to the update and actual provisioning of the connectivity service, while the 4th packet corresponds to it is acknowledged. After the user node has changed its position, we ask the TFS NBI to update the connectivity service in the 5th packet. The 6th packet correspond to the removal of the connection that the connectivity service has originated and the 7th to the removal of the connectivity service itself. The 8th packet corresponds to the setting up of the new connection while the final 9th packet is the ACK to the update of the service.

A large number of connectivity services have been requested to the TFS NBI to test the speed of the algorithm responsible for selecting the closest node. As we can see in Fig. 2.b, all requests were finished between 98 ms and 172 ms, fast enough to fulfill most use cases, with a mean of 0.137 ms and an standard deviation of 0.0185 ms.

Conclusions

This paper has presented the introduction of location-awareness in end-to-end connectivity services and in network topologies. The authors have proposed an augmented data model for topology and connectivity services to include GPS coordinates and Regions into service endpoints, as well as connectivity service constraints. The proposed architecture considers the requested end-to-end connectivity service provisioning and update taking into consideration that location-aware connectivity services might need service endpoint migration due to the dynamic nature of joint edge-cloud continuum. A break-before-make approach has been evaluated in ADRENALINE Testbed.

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